

ALIENATION, SUFFERING & DISORIENTATION IN FIRE ON THE MOUNTAIN

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Abstract:

Anita Desai shines as one of the great novelists India has ever produced. In the novel *Fire on the Mountain*, Anita Desai presents three various kinds of disoriented characters and attempts to search out their interrelations and differences. This is a story of three women: Carignano, the lonely villa in Kasauli exploring the alienation of the central character Nanda Kaul, the wife of the Vice-Chancellor, their great granddaughter Raka and her friend Ila Das. This novel chiefly concerns with the solitude and isolation, the subsequent anger and suffering in the lives of Nanda Kaul and Raka. In her novel, Anita Desai presents women not completely cut off from social and familial bindings but who while remaining within their orbits, protest against tedium, injustice and humiliation. In her novels, women are not a simple goddess or a robot but a self-actualizing and self-realizing individual.

Keywords: - Alienation, suffering, marital unhappiness, disorientation, frustration

Introduction:

The emergence of women novelists in Indian English literature took place as early as the last quarter of the nineteenth century. But, it was only after independence that they could make a solid contribution to Indian English fiction. The post-independence period has brought to the forefront a number of noted women novelists who have enriched Indian English fiction by a creative release of feminine sensibility. The woman has been the focus of many literary works in this period. Writers like Kamala Markandaya, Nayantara Sahgal, Ruth Prasad Jhabvala, Anita Desai, Shashi Deshpande etc. have achieved recognition in recent times. In the line of Ruth Prasad Jhabvala, Kamala Markandaya and Nargis Dutt, Anita Desai shines as one of the great novelists India has ever produced. To date she has written ten novels, twelve short stories, two books for children, and some reviews. Her novels include *Cry, the Peacock* (1963), *Voices in the City* (1965), *Bye-Bye Blackbird* (1971), *Where Shall We Go This Summer* (1975), *Fire on the Mountain* (1978), *Clear Light of the Day* (1984), *In Custody* (1984), and *Baumgartner's Bombay* (1988), *Journey to Ithaka* (1996), *Fasting Feasting* (1999) and *The Zigzag Way* (2004). With the novels to her credit, Anita Desai has added a new dimension to the performance of Indian women writers in English fiction. In Prasad Jhabvala's work the social background has more importance than the characters that play the different comedies, tragi-comedies and farces. In the work of Kamala Markandaya the emphasis is given more on the chief characters and on their different backgrounds such as economics, political, cultural or social. Whereas in Anita Desai's novels, the inner climate, the climate of sensibility that rumbles like thunder and suddenly glows like lightning, is more compelling than the outer weather, the physical geography or the visible action. In other words, her forte is the analysis of sensibility—a particular kind of modern Indian sensibility. Since her concern is with the inner world of sensibility instead of the outer world of action, she has tried to fabricate a style flexible and evocative enough to convey the excitement and agony of the stream of consciousness of her chief protagonists. The unbearable clash with thoughts, feelings and emotions is certainly reflected in the language, syntax and imagery, yet the reader's first impression on reading